

Costume And Make-Up in Dramatic Communication: The Superstory Example

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ABSTRACT

A drama text is a written presentation of the series of structured words and actions that form the play. Drama performances employ specific dramatic or theatrical elements to amplify or reveal significant yet concealed messages within the text. Costume and make-up are two elements of drama that can serve as powerful means of communication in dramatic productions. This paper emphasizes that in order for a director to effectively communicate through costume and make-up, the costumier/make-up artist must comprehend and value the expectations of the production, utilizing these elements to highlight the hidden meanings within the drama. This paper concludes that in any given play production, costume and make-up design, as vital elements of visual communication, must clarify characters, their relationships, and associations for the audience.

Keywords: Costume and Make-up, Audience, Communication, Theatrical Elements, and Drama.

Introduction:

A drama text is a written presentation of the series of structured words and actions that form the play. However, during a performance, the use of certain dramatic or theatrical elements serves to enhance or reveal important yet hidden messages within the text. The writer often implies these messages, which form the plot, without explicitly writing them in the scripts. We refer to these as theatrical elements, utilizing dance, music, props, costumes, and make-up to convey hidden meanings to the audience. In this study, we examine how drama directors and producers in Nigeria use two of these elements—costume and make-up—to enhance meanings in their works.

As Lilian Eguriase Bakare posits, “Costume materials and designs as well as signs, symbols, and their meanings make play performances meaningful” (p. 407). Costume and make-up are two elements of drama that can serve as very potent means of communication in dramatic productions. According to Okobia Adakole and Bakare Lilian E, costume and makeup are two of the four elements that comprise the visual scene or environment of a theatre performance (p. 101). Furthermore, it's important to recognize that, in addition to words and action, the application of these elements (costume and make-up) to production aids the viewer/audience in understanding and appreciating the message. Thus, performers have used costume and make-up, just like every other element of theatre, to enhance effective communication since ancient times.

Discussing costume and make-up in dramatic communication requires an appropriate understanding of what constitutes drama, communication, and the relationship between the two. Drama initiates life; it is a reproduction or reflection of life. It is the enactment of real and imagined events through action and dramatic competences. It freezes events in the time frame of the play. Drama exists to provide meaning and express ideas about the world we live in. Dolman, (1993:23).

Adanri (2005:109) posits that: “Drama is a self-contained dialectic, one that is free and redefined from moment to moment.” Drama is absolute. To be dramatic, it must break from everything that is external. It can be conscious of nothing outside itself. The dramatist is absent from drama. He doesn't speak during his initial conversation. Furthermore, according to her, drama is not written; it is set, and every line spoken in drama is a disclosure. Similarly, we could define communication as any method that conveys a thought from one individual to another. This medium facilitates the transfer of information from one individual to another, enabling both parties to comprehend themselves better.

This is applicable to dramatic communication. People generally understand that communication is the process of conveying a play's message to the audience through visual, verbal, and non-verbal elements, aiming to achieve the effect that the scriptwriter and producer/director envision.

Therefore, the instrument of costume and make-up contributes to dramatic communication, holding a unique position among visual aids. The actors/actresses physically wear costumes and make-up, which aids in role interpretation, enables easy recognition within the production's context, and provides artistic and aesthetic interpretation.

COSTUME

Just as there are different clothes for different occasions and different periods, so also is costume which sends signals similar to those of every life. Theatrical costume according to Wilson (1978:356...)

Communication information with regards to sex, position and occupation which are usually magnified because everything in theatre is in spotlight.

The first contact that audience has with a play production is scenery, then costume and make-up. They form a visual image in the consciousness of the audience in term of period, time style and create a metaphor of the play even before lines are rendered. Costume and make-up enhance spectacle in a dramatic context. Costume adds value of their own in terms of colour, shape; and more importantly symbolism to the overall effect. In buttressing this, Wilson opines that:

Costume and make-up determines the look of a production. They emphasize whether a production is realistic or non-realistic whether it is modern or historic they add colour and visual excitement (2002:97).

Costume and make-up aid the audience's understanding. It is when the audience understands the meaning of the actor's apparel and is able to interpret it that they can evaluate or enjoy a dramatic work. Again, Wilson (2002) observes that:

...of all the visual elements in theatre, costumes are the most personal because they are actually worn by the performers. Visually, performer and costume are perceived as one: merge into a single image on stage(iii).

The image which is revealed is the character involvement in the inner world of the play. That is, the costume of the wearer aids in assuming the identity of the character he is impersonating.

To express or identify the personality of a character, Ommanney et al (1982) also advocates that: costume reflects one's social status, taste idiosyncrasies". Also, the psychological nature of the character is revealed in the dress and make-up he or she is wearing. For example, the physical and mental disposition of a lunatic is revealed because of the things he does as reflected in the kind of clothes he wears. Costume and make-up portray the state of mind of the character and create a balance in the information communicated to the audience.

Furthermore, make-up, in particular helps to establish the required dramatic effect of communication by the act of believability it affords the audience. For instance, where there is a proper application of make-up the actor goes through less stress in order to be able to actualize and interpret the given role more effectively and more believably.

The issues raised above are illustrated below using a Nigerian Tele-drama Super Story as an example.

SUPERSTORY

Superstory is a popular Television drama programme created by Wale Adenuga in the year 2001, to reflect the daily realities of Nigeria life in all its ramification. It uses a Tele-novella (a serial in which one serie is told in several episodes) story concept. It is a depiction of the social, economic and political realities of the average Nigerian.

Since the Tele-novella conception and dramatic practice rely much on didacticism, Superstory ideological stand is not only to entertain but to inform, enlighten and communication socio-economic issues, cultural values and also prescribe possible remedies to social problems and anomalies using drama as a catalyst for social change.

Apart from projecting developmental issues, it substantially identifies with the poor and oppressed group in the society, depicting their existential anguish and unravelling their condition.

Superstory is presented on the M.T.A. Network between 8.00pm and 9:00pm every Thursday. The Tele-novella is produced by Wale Adenuga directed by AntarLaniyan. For the purpose of this paper, we are using **Oh Father O Daughter**, one of the productions of Superstory as a case study. It has eighteen episodes and ran for eighteen weeks on the N.T.A., Network in 2001, celebrating the Values and lifestyles of the common man.

Oh Father Oh Daughter

A synopsis of **Oh Father Oh Daughter** tells the Story of a commoner Suara, his wife Abike and two children who are victims of abject poverty in a morally and socio-economically bankrupt society.

However, Suara's wife, a rare and virtuous woman loves her poor husband dearly. In spite of their circumstances, she works hard within her means to sustain the family. Her submission towards the desires of her husband makes her to agree to sacrifice herself by acceptionChieftMolokwu's offer of having an affair with her before giving her husband a job. But the Chief repents of his action as a result of her disposition of faithfulness towards her husband.

Chief MolokwugiversSuara a job out of compassion. Suara, on his part, works very hard, becomes established, but soon forgets his past and begins to stay away from home. He frolicks with a promiscuous woman who convinces him to abandon his wife and children.

The new woman gradually siphons all his money. He returns to a new state of poverty deeper than the previous.

We shall now look at how the costumes and makeup of major characters in “Oh Father, Oh Daughter” have been used to communicate themes, character portrayals, and situations in the production.

Analysis of Costume and Make-up Scheme in Oh Father Oh Daughter

The simple dictum that “apparel often proclaims the Man” affirms that the cloth and other accessories a man wears portray his or her way of life. In other words, costume and make-up portray what an individual is. These include his/her professional, background and above all his/her personal idiosyncrasies.

Suara is the lead character and he has a perfect costume for each mood and period of the play as well as age, status and personality, family and social strata of the character. His poor clothing at the beginning comprising of faded old blue long sleeve shirt with inner Polo shirt and cream coloured loose trouser with a white knitted Cap, aptly captures his poverty-struck status. There is an intelligent use of dull and blind colours to depict his daily routine; searching for menial jobs.

With his new status, his dressing improves tremendously and the result of this is proper distribution of colour, line, shape and texture. As a result of his disposition, he is not given to too much flamboyancy in his costume, his costume also portrays him as a Yoruba-Man as well as give us a cursory glance into his social strata through the play.

His initial use of faded blue long sleeve shirt and cream trousers as well as knitted Cap quite captures his state of mind. It portrays him as someone disenchanted with life. A combination of these colours i.e. white and Navy blue is sometimes used in our society to represent sadness and a person that is down cast. Green and white, depicts life while brown represents earth. A combination of these colours for Suara’s costumes when his status improved is quite effective as it gives the viewer an appropriate appreciation of the character.

In make-up, Suara’s character suffers. A character make-up where more stress lines are emphasized showing his frustration and his state of mind at the time of poverty and then a straight make-up to enliven his features when his fortune improves would have been appropriate in order to help accentuate his features and communicate to the audience the various stages of his experience. The permanent feature both in times of want and times of plenty is misleading.

In spite of this oversight however, Suara’s transformation through costume and a proper arrangement of the design i.e. colour, line, texture and shape was well positioned to communicate as well as create a degree of emotional response from the viewer.

Suara's modest wife **Abike**, is an ideal Yoruba housewife and this is typified by her costume. As first contact with her, she is wearing a mixture of red and yellow flowering Ankara (African print) buba blouse on a white colour Iro (Wrapper) and the gele (head tie) is of yellow shade, just like her husband's they are faded and threadbare. This signifies abject poverty. Although in spite of her extreme state of poverty, she still manages to dress decently with what she can afford in order to maintain her dignity as a woman.

When her husband becomes jobless and they cannot afford the basic necessity of life such as good food, clothing and children's School fees, her dress combination is made up of red and yellow flowery Ankara (African print) buba blouse on a white background Iro (Wrapper) and yellow gele (head tie). When their status improves we see her with good quality Ankara, laces and Satin materials with the choice of cool regal colours of blue, purple, pink and yellow mixed with green patches designed into Iro and embroidered Bubu gowns and straight shirts and blouse with head gear of same fabrics.

Abike does not go into any flamboyant display of jewelleries as she is a modest woman with a sense of decency. Abike's choice of costume are quite impressive and realistic, she gives a picture of one who is into influenced by material things. **Abike's** make-up is characterized and therefore quite realistic. Her make-up is also in stages.

First state: Dark coloured foundation powder is used to cover the actors light and shiny facial complexion and black eye pencil is used to emphasize stress lines on her face. This depicts abject poverty.

Second stage: A higher stage of base powder which made the face radiant and cheerful with a brown line which gives an impression of cheerfulness comfortable. And a character make-up of one who is indisposed and recovering after her husband has abandoned here.

Toyin

Her expensive and flamboyant fabrics depict here as a fashionable woman of high taste and class. In her first appearance she wears a long flowery skirt and sleeveless blouse made from sky-blue plain voile fabric with a head tie of the same fabric. She is ornamented with assorted beaded jewelleries on her wrist and neck while her ear rings are of silver and gold huer expensive and flamboyant fabrics depicts her as fashionable woman of high taste and class. In her first appearance she wears a long flowery skirt and sleeveless blouse made from sky-blue plain voile fabric with a head tie of the same fabric. She is ornamented with assorted beaded jewelleries on her wrist and neck while her earrings are of silver and gold hue.

Subsequently, she dons different shade of expensive laces and voile sewn into Iro and buba brocade, beautiful flowery African prints sewn into skirts and blouses, damask headgear, gold jewelries, beads, handbags and shoes of different colour and sizes.

Her choice of costume and make-up which comprise of bright loud and flamboyant colours communicate her to the viewer as one who is vain and a woman of the world who does not bother about modesty nor care about anyone but herself and what she can get from others in order to maintain her desires and ambition. Her costume is quite effective for her characterization.

Toyin wears a character make-up of light-coloured base because of her complexion, which brings her lip-line out prominently. Her make-up is properly applied and in tune with her character.

Chief Molokwu

He is man of wealth with bold loud colours to communicate his personality. He is an Igbo chief. He is presented in the Igbo (Isi-Agu) black and gold coloured velvet top, sewn bogously and black trouser to give the wearer a confident look. At another time we see him in white and turquoise blue glower lace material sewn into agbada, buba and sokoto with a red cap to match. And finally, a grey gabardine material sewn as a trouser and a big buttoned shirt with a cap. All his costumes are worn with red neck heads which portray him as an Igbo chief. His make-up is very simple. His costume and make-up are effective and realistic because the viewer is presented with a man who is sure of himself and backed by his wealth.

Mrs Molokwu

A high-class woman with wealth and means at her disposal. She appears just once and it is remarkable. She is in Iro and Buba made from lace fabric of lemon green background which is bold and with a mixture of red and blue flowery design. Her colour composition depicts life and contentment. Her make-up is a light foundation powder, two different shades of blue and purpose eye shadow a touch of pink on the cheekbones, red colour lipstick with her hairstyle laid out in curls. Her characterization as a rich and gorgeous woman is well communicated.

Suara's father

At first, we see him in a cream coloured minimally embroidered guinea brocade danshiki with a black trouser and black cap to match.

Secondly, in rich looking blue brocade sewn into agbada, short sleeve top and sokoto with a white and blue coloured matching top. His costume contradicts his character as he is supposed to be poor but still looks richly dressed as opposed to his son who is responsible for his upkeep. His costume choice is not effective because it is not a realistic reflection of his status. His make-up is not clearly defined as the son looks older than him. Dramatic communication is ineffective here because his make-up contradicts the actions and age in the production.

Uncle Caleb

He is a typical village farmer whose costumes portray his character. A grey coloured simple Ankara (African print) sewn into abuba top and sokoto with a handmade cap, and another cream coloured sleeveless top with a three quarter trouser (jumper) as the totality of his costumes, his choice of colour is appropriate because it presents him to the viewer as one who is not overbearing but rather of subdued temperament. His make-up is a simple straight one whereby foundation powder is used to enhance his facial features and this is very consistent with his character.

Abike's Children

Dayo

We see him in a grey coloured and tattered material for a shirt with a knicker which he constantly supports with his hand. At some point, he is without a shirt just a threadbare faded knicker. With the improvement in their fortune, he is seen in a blue long sleeve shirt with well sewn black trousers. He has no visible make-up except for his smart haircut as an older boy.

Bukky

She is seen in a cream coloured threadbare gown made from flowery cotton material and a white and deep blue coloured blouse and a skirt of black hue. Just like her brother, she changes with a father's new found fortunes, into a multi-coloured flowery Ankara fabric sewn into skirt and blouse in a befitting style for girls of her age. **Bukky's** make-up as in the case of her brother is neither special nor visible.

Abike's houseboy who is dressed casually in a short brown coloured knicker with a white half singlet and a brown coloured towel always across his shoulder gives a realistic impression of his status as a domestic help. Obed is another character whose make-up is neglected. A bit of character make-up would have further conveyed the stress he is going through especially in the hand of Bukky.

Landlord

His mode of dressing reflects his personality as a no non-sense and shrewd businessman. He is dressed in embroidered agbada, top and sokoto made from a brilliant green and yellow coloured lace fabric. His facial features are enhanced with a straight make-up which is well applied and articulated to give the character a realistic definition.

Critical comment

In as much as the costumes and make-up are appropriate in certain situations there are some other situations where seemingly lack of professional attention to costume and make-up sent wrong information. For example at some point, we found Mrs. Molokwu to be overdressed which is not appropriate. There are scenes where she is costumed as if she is going for a ceremony. Meanwhile, she is just lounging at home. It would have been more

convincing at this point if she is wearing a regular house wear despite her status. Her flamboyance is also becoming rather overblown in her make-up, since someone sitting at home need not wear a heavy flamboyant make-up meant for a ceremony.

The same can be said of **Abike** (Suara's wife) whose costume and make-up sometimes contradict her personality and characterization. For instance, in the scene where she is ill, her costume and make-up are rather gorgeous and do not depict that of somebody who is being taken to the hospital. She should have been soberly dressed to portray her stat at that point in time.

Another case is **Suara's** father, we are made to understand that it is his son **Suara** who is responsible for his upkeep. This is not portrayed in his costume. In most instances, he is more richly dressed than Suara himself.

Conclusion

This paper aims to explore the role of costume and make-up in enhancing meanings and their potent role in dramatic communication when applied appropriately in productions. In order for a director to achieve his or her vision/objective of achieving communication through the use of costume and make-up, the costumier/make-up artist should understand and appreciate what is expected of him or her in a given production, using these two elements to bring to the fore the hidden meanings in the drama. In any given play production, costume and make-up design, as vital elements of visual communication, must clarify characters, their relationships, and associations for the viewers.

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